

Development of Smart Wheelchair using IoT

Bachelors of Science in Electrical Engineering

Areeba Shabbir EE151004

Aneesa Abbas EE151008

Rasool Hamza Rao EE151043

Session: 2015-2019

Department of Electrical Engineering
Faculty of Engineering

Khwaja Fareed University of Engineering and
Information Technology
Rahim Yar Khan

February, 2020

Development of Smart Wheelchair using IoT

By

Areeba Shabbir EE151004

Aneesa Abbas EE151008

Rasool Hamza Rao EE151043

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for degree of

Bachelors of Science in Electrical Engineering

Supervisor: Engr. Arslan Hassan

Department of Electrical Engineering
Faculty of Engineering

Khwaja Fareed University of Engineering and
Information Technology
Rahim Yar Khan

February, 2020

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Areeba Shabbir (EE151004):

Signature: _____

Aneesa Abbas (EE151008):

Signature: _____

Rasool Hamza Rao (EE151043):

Signature: _____

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Supervisor Name: Engr. Arslan Hassan

Signature: _____

Co-Supervisor Name: Engr. Maira Alvi

Signature: _____

External Examiner:

Signature: _____

Name of the HoD: Engr. Dr. Shahid Atiq

Signature: _____

Acknowledgements

We would be very thankful to our supervisor "**Engr. Arslan Hassan**" and co-supervisor "**Engr. Maira Alvi**" for their virtuous and technical support that made us capable to complete this project in an effective manner. We are greatly thankful to the faculty of Electrical Engineering for providing support and guidance. We would also like to thank the laboratory staff of the Electrical Department for their help in providing us the resources.

We are thankful to **ALLAH** Almighty for helping us in the completion of the project. We feel privileged to extend our deep sense of gratitude to our parents for their support and encouragement. Without them it is likely we would not be on this project. Last but not the least, we are thankful to all the friends who encouraged us in completing this project partially.

Abstract

With the advancement of technology assisted robots for disable humans have been designed in the world to enhance their confidence for spending life like normal humans. The project is developed to help those who are facing difficulties in movement such as people who met with accidents and end up with paralyzed legs, physically disabled or injured people, Project is designed to develop a smart wheelchair to facilitate the people with disabilities. Micro-controller is the main controlling component that controls the whole wheelchair. The designed project is multi-mode offering control interfaces of app control, voice control, gesture control and joystick control to control the wheelchair movement. A patient health care system is also designed in this wheelchair which allows the patient to measure his heart rate and also contain a system that helps the caretakers to understand the needs of the person . Another feature of the designed system is the live streaming and location tracing. Using live streaming feature, a real time activity/video of a wheelchair can be monitored by the caretaker and its location can also be traced. This product not only allows the handicapped people to control the wheelchair by themselves without help from others but also allows other people to use the android phone (remote control) to control the wheelchair. Obstacle detection system is incorporated in the smart wheelchair which works if an emergency condition occurs. Qibla direction finder is also available in the smart wheelchair. The designed wheelchair system will

pay more attention to the health safety of the disabled person. This project has an advanced feature like patient health care system, live streaming, Qibla direction finder and obstacle detection system as compared to existing smart wheelchair.

Keywords: Smart Wheelchair; Disabled Person; Patient Care System; Live Streaming; IoT

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1 Introduction

In the modern era, due to technological advancement robots are becoming more popular. Due to increasing demands of robots, robotics technology is increasing day by day. Robotics is the capstone of current technological advancement. This branch of engineering is primarily associated with the knowledge of fabrication of sensors, knowledge of engineering, techniques of manufacturing, construction and modern algorithms. Due to modernization in robotic technologies, several new styles and mechanisms are being enforced that are ready to scan human thoughts and perceive actions. Such robots notice large applications in helpful robotics e.g. to assist out injured, sick and older folks. Advancement in technology has totally changed the people way of living. Nowadays people rely more on technology but there are people who are unable to get benefit from this development. On particular people with limited mobility are still suffering. They are living a miserable life. To facilitate such type of people smart wheelchairs are introduced. These wheelchairs are powered wheelchairs that uses batteries and motors to derive the chair. In the past people uses manually driven wheelchairs that require man power for driving. It was difficult task for most of the disabled persons because more energy and physical strength is required to derive such type of wheelchairs. Some disabled people also have weaker upper limbs so it is more difficult for them to use hand driven wheelchairs. Also using such type of wheelchair more time is required to reach the

destination. Therefore, to provide ease of mobility to such people powered wheelchairs are introduced. These powered wheelchairs have the capabilities of control and navigational intelligence.

There are many people who are not aware of the advancement that robotic technology has made also people of old ages were not aware of this technology. But the truth is that since 1930s such robots have been developed that are serving the handicapped people. In 1930s an electrically propelled tricycle was introduced and was invented by George Klein after World War II to provide ease for disabled persons.

The work proposed in this report focuses on the development of a multi-functional Wheelchair for handicapped. It is helpful for the physically disabled persons. Micro-controller is the main controlling unit. the designed multi-mode wheelchair has controlling features of app control, voice control, joystick control and gesture control. It also includes patient health care system. Obstacle detection system is incorporated in the smart wheelchair which works if an emergency condition occurs. Qibla direction finder is also available in the wheelchair system. It also includes some advance features like live streaming and location tracing for monitoring purposes.

1.1 Project Background

Physical disabilities either temporary or permanent has led to an increase in the demand for wheelchairs. From the last few decades, smart wheelchair is the quite popular and many technological advancement has been made in it. According to World Report on Disability there are about 70 million handicapped people in the world. These persons require assistance in the fulfilment of their daily needs. For this purpose there is a need of intelligent wheelchair

system that will be beneficial for people with any type of disability. Hand driven wheelchair was developed in the past but it was energy consuming also physical strength is required to drive such wheelchairs. Nowadays motorized or powered wheelchairs are developed to provide ease of mobility. These chairs uses motors and batteries to drive the wheelchair by reducing human efforts. Many type of wheelchairs are developed for different type of disabled persons but the wheelchair we are going to made is multi-functional having advance features. This wheelchair designed is multi mode having health care, live streaming and location tracing features. Caretaker can monitor the live activity of the wheelchair through live streaming feature.

1.2 Project Objectives

The objectives of our project are

- To study the literature of smart wheelchairs.
- To explore about future of auto wheelchairs.
- Development of smart wheelchair.
- Designing a cost effective smart wheelchair.
- To know itâs working.
- Provide ease for disabled.
- To know its working conditions and operating speed.
- Experimental analysis.

1.3 Applications

There are several applications where intelligent wheelchair can be used.

- Hospitals
- Old age home
- Health care centers
- At home for physically handicapped individuals
- Can be used for performing umrah/hajj
- Can be used in airports, bus stops etc.
- In shopping malls as shopping trolleys
- In industries as robot to carry goods

1.4 Limitations

- Can't move above its rated speed.
- Not suitable in rainy conditions.
- Can't carry weight heavier than the defined range.

2 Literature Review

This chapter presents literature review on the development of smart wheelchair. The advancement of the multi-mode smart wheelchair that aim to help disable people to move freely is discussed.

2.1 Wheelchair History

The wheelchair is considered as a type of facility that is used by many of people around the world with different disabilities such that paralysis, broken legs, chronic pain, fatigue and much more. If we study the history of the wheelchair that represent to some extent the power of inventions and collaboration between disabled people and innovators, and also describe the importance of this new innovations.

While the concept of chairs and wheels have been introduced thousands of years, the Ancient Greeks and the Chinese were the first one who had the idea to combine the both. Ancient Greeks were also well known for their chariots, and their history shows that they also used wheeled bed for disable person to carry those were not able to walk. In China, wheelchairs are being used since 525 AD. King Philip II of Spain, during his reigned from 1527-1595, he used a wheelchair which was operating by arm and foot [1]. There is another invention in

Germany in 1665, Stephen Farfler, who was a paraplegic watchmaker, design such wheelchair that could operate by self-having three wheels and having a hand crank fitted on the front wheels. The X frame, very similar to models are still in use nowadays, was invention of two engineer friends, Herbert Everest and Harry Jennings, who were handicapped. They want to build such chair which could be fold and could carry in the car, so they built it in 1933. Canadian George Klein and his team are recognized by inventing first motorized wheelchair. His idea was to develop it in the 1950s to help World War II veterans [2].

So nowadays there is also being used electric powered wheelchairs for the ease of disabled people. They are being used from the last 20 years. So according to the demand of consumer of wheelchair, by hand wheelchairs, electronic wheelchairs, and automated wheelchairs are being used to fulfil the user's demand. The development in advancement of wheelchair has been start over the past 1000 years, and till now different structural changes have been made according to the requirement.

2.2 Wheelchair Technology Previous Development

Limited mobility is considered as the almost common disability among young and full blown, so a manual mode wheelchair is frequently recommended to label these restrictions. Nowadays due to increase in development of technology so many types of electric wheelchairs have been designed like voice controlled, gesture controlled, mind controlled etc. which are described below in detail.

2.2.1 Voice Activated Wheelchair Controller

Rockland (1998) has the talent to think the idea to design voice-controlled wheelchair. This type of project was designed as a solution of low-cost system for the sake of creating prototype

for operating a wheelchair [3]. A microcontroller was used having programming through user control each command, and safe the voice from distortion. AES Corporation's microcontroller AES-88 act as the main controlling unit, like CPU. And there is a seven segment displays where the output from the SRS came. Since each word is coded with a specific number in controller. The microcontroller program consists of a table, with the specific word having associated number respectively. Instead of voice control, the wheelchair movement can also be controlled through web based GUI wirelessly if the internet is available [4].

2.2.2 Autonomous Robotic Wheelchair Controller Using Embedded Systems

Chung, Hung (2007) designed Autonomous Robotic Wheelchair with the help of Embedded Systems [5]. This robotic wheelchair consists of the facility of obstacle detection, user friendly interactions, location navigation, when compared to other powered wheelchairs being used. Most of researches used their own computer and CPU for the operation of wheelchair but due to large size of PC and high-power consumption it is not recommended. With the use of embedded system, the designed wheelchair shows its qualities of reliability, low power usage whereas on the other hand there is also a benefit of coding and high-speed computing capacity circumstances are also managed. The fuzzy logic-based map reading system are combined simultaneously to solve appropriate condition of such wheelchairs.

2.2.3 Smart Wheelchair operated using Joystick

The primary key points of the research and innovation responsible in electronic wheelchair controller by hand operated joystick was to inquire the use of harmful control technique to

help disabled wheelchair consumer. By the movement of joystick the potentiometer convert analog voltage and using analog data pins transfer it to the controller. The Arduino receive these signals and send it to to analog to digital convertor further procedure. Here analog values are converted to digital signal. Motor driving IC accept this signal through digital output pin. The command is applied by the use of joystick and then there is a need to send data in microcontroller (ATMega328p) for further processing of the given command. After this the motor driving IC receives digital signal from microcontroller and control the movement of motors according to the commands given by the joystick [6]. Instead of conventional joystick, intelligent joystick is also been in use which is based on the fuzzy logic combinations [7]. This type of wheelchair also ensures safety of the disabled person.

2.2.4 Hand Motion Controlled Smart Wheelchair

In 1977 Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) introduced another technique for controlling the motion of wheelchair through hand movement. They used principal glove model. And it was put forwarding by theâ Computerized Entry Data GloveaË designed by Gary Grimes in 1983. The principal glove contains utilization of numerous sensors. H. Kazerooni et al. also put effort in the advancement of a gadget called âThe Magic Gloveâ [8]. The âMagic Gloveâ is such kind of a glove with a different variety of usage in the area of applied instrumentations. The gloveâs basically function is to measures the force applied by the user of a material having robot. So, the force is detected by controller and it is communicated towards measuring. The bearing capacity of glove is to be able the user to apply an insignificant force on an object while carrying it starting from one place towards next. The human itself or the user of these gloves just mimics the movement to be done, while the real lifting and adjustment is left for the controller to be complete. The wheelchair

movement can also be controlled automatically through the use of acceleration sensors and an obstacle detection system is also designed to ensure the safety [9]. The hand gesture control can also be made wireless through the use of RF transmitter and receiver making the system self-reliable [10].

2.2.5 Head Motion Controlled Electric Wheelchair

The Head-motion Controlled Wheelchair is far better than conventional Wheelchairs. In this project, Accelerometer MPU6050 is attached to ear-set, which will detect the motion of head. This accelerometer, works on X-Y axis, so when the head is moved in either of the four directions i.e. right or left, forward or backward, this change the axis of accelerometer from its reference point. Then, this data is transferred to ATmega328p micro controller, and microcontroller sends the received signal from transmitter to the receiver end. This microcontroller is interfaced with the motor driver. Microcontroller sends Interrupt signal to the motor driver and hence wheelchair moves according to the motion of head [11]. The wheelchair motion can also be controlled according to user intention through the use of digital signal processing technique. [12]. This technique will help to create user friendly interface.

2.2.6 Mind Controlled Wheelchair

When robotic wheelchair joint brain control with artificial intelligence, then bring such sort of innovation to make it easier for others by using only their ideas. The idea, considered is that the microcontroller is pre-programmed according to given command that could help disabled people by turning crude brain signals through more complex commands. Signals taken from eyes and brain are send to controller for processing, which is used to control th wheelchair. EEG (Electroencephalography) approach is used that contains the procedure of installation of

an electrode cap, which is necessary for data acquisition of these signal and this electrode is placed on the person scalp. The electrode receive signal which take over by EEG CAP and sent commands for movement through the Arduino which is pre-programmed and help to move the wheelchair [13]. The conventional wheelchair is not suitable for people who are paralyzed below neck. So interfacing the powered wheelchair with brain serves the purpose. This works by taking signals through user brain and the frequency of the blinks of the eye and after processing these signals performs functions according to the set commands [14].

Figure 2.1: Mind Controlled Smart Wheelchair

3 Project Design

3.1 Project Description

Smart wheelchair is micro-controller based in which Atmega 2560 is used as a micro-controller. This micro-controller is programmed to give commands to different components to perform their tasks. All the components give output as they are programmed for. Here two batteries (each one is 12V) are used to supply power to different parts of the system. BTS 7960B module is used to control the motors. There are four mode of operation to operate the wheelchair. The first one is mobile app control. In app control the wheelchair will be controlled using app, there are buttons on the app dashboard to control the wheelchair direction. The second one is joystick control in which wheelchair will be controlled using joystick that is placed on the arm of the wheelchair. The third mode is voice control. the fourth one is gesture control in which wheelchair is controlled using the gyroscope of mobile. The smart wheelchair is also designed keeping in mind the health safety of the disabled person. Patient health care system helps the caretaker to understand the disabled person needs and allows the patient to measure his heart rate. An additional feature of the designed wheelchair system is live streaming and location tracing. The live streaming feature shows the live video and the location of the wheelchair to the person at home for monitoring purpose.

3.2 Block Diagram

Figure 3.1 shows the block diagram of the smart wheelchair system.

Figure 3.1: Block Diagram of Smart Wheelchair

3.3 Hardware Description

Hardware components are the main part of the project implementation. The detail of the components used in project is given below:

- Atmega 2560 Microcontroller
- ESP32 CAM Module
- Bluetooth Module
- Heart Rate Sensor

- LCD Display
- Motor Driver Shield
- Hex Keypad
- DC Brushed Motors
- GPS Module
- Ultrasonic Sensor
- Joystick
- Battery
- Digital Compass

3.3.1 Atmega 2560 Microcontroller

This micro-controller is based on the RISC architecture having 8 bits. It contains 54 digital I/O pins. Out of which 16 are used as analog pins (to give signal in analog form) and 4 hardware serial ports and 15 can be used as pwm. It has also crystal oscillator of 16 MHz (for generating electrical signal of particular frequency), a power jack, a reset button (to clear memory) and a USB connection. It includes each and everything which is required to run the microcontroller. Through a USB cable it is being in contact with computer and then for giving power it is connected to AC to-DC adapter to start the microcontroller. There is also an external supply can be used which should be of 6 to 20 volts, at which board can operate easily. Supply of less voltages like 7 volt as compared to 5V pin, it may cause the board to become unstable

Figure 3.2: Atmega 2560 Micro-controller

3.3.2 ESP32 CAM Module

The ESP32-CAM Module is such type of module which contains an OV2640 camera and ESP32-S chip. And there are many GPIOs to connect supplemental .To store files or images which are taken from camera, a micro SD card slot is considered as useful. For video streaming face recognition, and detection of something a web server is set up to do all tasks smoothly. In this project it is used to give location of wheelchair to the person at home for monitoring purpose.

Figure 3.3: ESP32 CAM Module

3.3.3 Bluetooth Module

For wireless communication Bluetooth module is designed in this project. To check the Bluetooth connection status a red LED affixed which shows, whether the HC-05 is in connecting

state or not.

Figure 3.4: Bluetooth Module

There are some signs to show the behavior of LED like red LED blinks continuously in a specific period of time when is it not connected to other HC-05 module, and it blinks slowly to two seconds if any other device is connected to this module. In this project to communicate smart phone with HC-05 Bluetooth module, smart phone requires Blue- tooth application for transmitting and receiving data. Bluetooth module is used in this project to connect the wheelchair with mobile for app control.

3.3.4 Heart Rate Sensor

Heart rate sensor is such type of sensor which is used to measures heart rate per minute by using the LED light sensor and optical LED.. When user hold the sensor the light of sensor shines through skin, and the reflected back light is being measured by sensor in the form of Beats. As light passed by blood pulses under the skin the reflected light vary. These variations of the reflected light are considered as heartbeats. Change of the intensity of light is based on the change of volume of blood in an organ so changed the heartbeats which is monitored by heart rate sensor.

3.3.5 LCD Display

It is used to display data on screen, finds in huge variety of applications in many embedded projects. It is mostly finds in other multi segment LEDs and also being preferred over seven

Figure 3.5: LCD Display

segments. In a 16x2 LCD, 16 characters can be displayed on one line but there are total 2 lines on it. They are mostly used because of the low cost and easy to program. In this LCD, each character will be made of 58 Pixel Dots. It has two registers. One is called Command and other is called Data register.

3.3.6 Motor Driver Shield

For motor driver application, the BTS7960B is used for high current applications. It contains p and n channel MOSFET of high and low-side respectively. It also contains a driver IC integrated in a single package and also part of the Novalith ICTM family. It is become easy to interface microcontroller with integrated driver IC which containing many features like, over current, logic level inputs, dead time generation, under voltage, diagnosis with current sense, protection against short circuit, over temperature, over voltage and slew rate adjustment.

There are many application of BTS7960B like it is used in sun roof, seat positioning, power windows, central door lock, wiper etc.

Figure 3.6: Motor Driver Shield

3.3.7 Hex Keypad

This 3x4 keypad contains 12 buttons which is arranged like a telephone-line 3x4 grids. It is

Figure 3.7: Hex Keypad

made up of narrow, adjustable membrane material containing adhesive backing to attach with other material where you want to attach. These 12 keys on the pad are connected like matrix form. To scan the pad only 7 micro-controller pins are needed 3 pins for columns and 4 pins for rows operation. The rows and columns are connected in such manner that the row are used as output and the column are used as input.

3.3.8 Brushed DC Motor

It is an electric motor which is designed and manufactured maintaining a precision speed motor output and produce high torque. This motor has the capacity to supply torque three to four times more than its rated value of torque. It can also supply up to five times as compared to its rated value without stalling, according to user requirement. It contains different components such as: the axle, rotor, commutator, magnets, stator, and brushes. To give power a magnetic drive to operate the armature of motor, this motor provides continuous current using rings. Probably, the Brushed DC Motor is generally used because of its capability to change the ratio of the speed-torque.

3.3.9 GPS Module

GPS a Global Positioning System is basically considered as totally satellite-based system which uses ground station and satellites to compute and measure its position on Earth surface. There is a requirement for GPS receiver that it needs to acquire data from at minimum 4 satellites for satisfied accuracy purpose. Antenna and others tiny processors are the part of GPS module that receive data through exclusive FR frequencies sent by satellites. After that GPS receiver in this module senses these signals. It calculate the distance of that signal from four satellites and then riddle out where are you. GPS receiver determine the location in three dimensions such that altitude, north and east.

3.3.10 Ultrasonic Sensor

It is a sensor mostly used for obstacle detection as it measures the object's distance from the sensor (reference point). Sound waves are used to measure the distance of the object. An high

frequency sound pulse is send through the transmitter when it strike the object it reflect back.

The 2 circle on the sensor front are used for transmitting and receiving purpose.

Figure 3.8: Ultrasonic Sensor

One of them act as a transmitter and the other opening act as a receiver. Here in our case these sensors are used as an obstacle detection unit which stops the wheelchair if it encounters any obstacle.

3.3.11 Joystick

To control the direction of wheelchair a joystick is used. Joysticks consist of two parts which are a base and a stick which help to move the wheelchair in any direction. User can move stick slowly and speedily and in different amount. As there is a flexible movement of joystick so it can also rotate left or right .It is much efficient to control the joystick than the keys on keyboard. For operation of joystick it is connected to computer by a USB or serial port connection and then with the help of software it is programmed according to assigned tasks of the button.

3.3.12 Battery

Lead Acid Battery is actually rechargeable battery which is used extensively in many projects to power the components. In this project two lead acid battery of 12V is used because motors require 12V for its working. All the other components are powered through a designed power source giving supply of 5V to them. Lead acid battery is the most inexpensive and efficient battery having higher voltage and lower cost.

3.3.13 Digital Compass

To find geographic direction a device used named as digital compass. For horizontally scaling it contains magnetic needle or needles which is also used to free to rotate until put in order with the earth's magnetic field. Digital compass is considered as the most accurate and perfect smart compass and also there is huge variety tool for outdoor activities. Digital compass will let you know the direction of Qibla which a person faces throughout the travelling period. In this project digital compass is used to facilitate the Muslims in finding the Qibla direction.

4 Methodology

The flow of the designed project is shown in the flow chart in Figure 4.1 below.

Figure 4.1: Flowchart of Overall Project

4.1 Circuit Design

Project circuit is made with the designed developer board i.e. I/O board, two motor driver modules (BTS 7960), Bluetooth module, joystick, digital compass, ultrasonic sensor, heart rate sensor, LCD display, speed controller (potentiometer), camera module and GPS module.

PWM pins for both motor driver are connected to micro-controller for PWM output configuration. The R-PWM and L-PWM of motor driver 1 are connected to Pin D3 and D6 while pin D10 and D13 are used for motor driver 2. Direction of the motors are controlled using R-EN and L-EN pins. Direction pins of motor driver 1 are connected to pin D4 and D7 of the micro-controller while D11 and D14 are used for motor driver 2.

Figure 4.2: Circuit Diagram of the Project

Two dry batteries each of 12V are used for power supply for the DC motors. Pin D0 and D1 are

used for Bluetooth module to transmit and receive data to and from micro-controller. Power supply for the Bluetooth module are from +5V and GND pins of the micro-controller. The X and Y coordinates of the joystick are connected to A4 and A5 of the I/O board respectively. The SDA and SCL pins of digital compass are attached to analog pins A6 and A7 of the microcontroller respectively. Ultrasonic sensors used for the obstacle detection are connected to D70 to D79 pins of the microcontroller. LCD display is connected to digital pins D26 to D31.

Figure 4.3: Circuit Diagram of the Live Streaming

Figure 4.3 shows ESP32 is a controller used for live streaming system. Camera module used

for live streaming purpose is attached to pin CSI D0 â CSI D7 of the microcontroller. Pin no. 8, 12, 16, 18, 19, 20 22 of the camera module are attached to PCLK, MCLK, HSYNC, VSYNC, RST, SCK SDA of the ESP32 microcontroller respectively.

4.2 Software Implementation

After the circuit design completion, by using the designed I/O board module, the coding for wheelchair is designed by using the programming software such as Microsoft Visual Studio. Microsoft Visual Studio was installed in this project that is used for software implementation and to program the designed wheelchair system. Software implementation flowchart is shown below in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Software Implementation Flowchart

4.3 Hardware implementation

Hardware implementation involves the electronic part. The electronic part includes the development of the circuitry for the overall project can be called as control box. The hardware circuitry or control box consist of designed developer board i.e. I/O board, motor driver and all the other components used in the project. There is a mode controller to choose the mode of operation of the designed wheelchair system. User can select the mode of operation of his own desire. There is a potentiometer to control the speed of the wheelchair. Bluetooth module is used to communicate with the main micro-controller to control the wheelchair directly from android phone. Voice commands from the android phone are used for the voice control operation. Camera and GPS are used for live streaming and location tracing respectively whereas digital compass is used to find the Qibla direction.

Figure 4.5: Control Box

In patient health care system Keypad is used to display the needs of the person and LCD is used to display that needs. Heart rate sensor is also used in patient health care system to

measure his heart rate. Joystick is used to control the wheelchair. Ultrasonic sensor is used for obstacle detection. There are two battery box each battery is of 12V, are placed into the box to ease the user to recharge the battery. Motor drivers are connected to battery using multi-core wire of 2.5mm diameter. Multi-core wire having a diameter of 2.5mm is used to bear high ampere supply to the motor drivers.

5 Testing & Results

The designed wheelchair system is tested for all the implemented features. Wheelchair testing steps are given below.

5.1 Testing of Wheelchair Movement

The designed wheelchair system has different mode of operation depicted in the block diagram given in Figure 5.1. The movement of wheelchair is tested using all the designed mode of operations.

Figure 5.1: Block Diagram of Mode Selection

Movement of the wheelchair is according to the pin configuration at motor driver. There are four buttons in the android app. Which are used to control the direction of wheelchair in forward, reverse, left and right. The directions of motion of both the wheels are given below in the table.

Button Command	Left Wheel	Right Wheel	Condition of Wheelchair
↑	Forward	Forward	Move Forward
↓	Reverse	Reverse	Reverse
⇒	Forward	Reverse	Move Right
⇐	Reverse	Forward	Move Left

Table for the Movement of Wheelchair

In mobile app control the wheelchair is controlled using mobile app. The app is used to give commands to the Wheelchair through Bluetooth. There are set values in the code for the movement of wheelchair. Bluetooth receive this signal and send to micro=controller to take action accordingly. Below given is the flow diagram of the mobile app control.

Figure 5.2: Flow Diagram of App Control

5.2 Development Stages

5.2.1 Initial prototype Development

In our main goal towards the initial work, firstly we have tested our components and taken information how to interface these equipment in our project. So developed a prototype of this project. In this prototype we have controlled the direction and movement of wheelchair through micro-controller which is used for communication with the wheelchair. In this way controller gives signal to the system, so system follows the given direction.

Figure 5.3: Initial Prototype of the Project

5.2.2 Hardware Development

This phase of the project includes the proposed feature. In initial stage prototype is designed to check the components, after testing all parameter there is a need to implement these components. This stage includes the implemented feature like Mobile app control, voice control, gesture and joystick control. There is also some additional feature i.e. live streaming and location tracing of the wheelchair to monitor the real time activity of the wheelchair with

its location. A patient health care system, obstacle detection and Qibla direction finder is also available in the smart wheelchair system.

5.2.3 Testing and Analysis of Hardware

After developing these feature there is a need to test this designed hardware. There is a check point either we have achieve our proposed target or not. So verification is necessary to take the record of analysis. Below figure shows the whole project development.

Figure 5.4: Flow Diagram of Different Stages of the Project

5.3 User Interface

There is a need of device for disabled people that help them for everyday workout, as it is difficult for them to move freely. Therefore, to provide comfort to disabled people, such an app is selected that shares an interface that gives approach to all the functions required by the user to control the wheelchair requiring the less effort.

5.3.1 Mobile App Interface

In mobile app control the wheelchair is controlled through mobile app.

Figure 5.5: Remote Control App Interface

The electronic parts and android application of the project must be communicated correctly for proper functioning of the system. Tested the selected Android application to control the motion and direction of wheelchair. The app is used to control the wheelchair through Bluetooth module. The way adopted this type of interfacing is the best way because it is user friendly and easy to access. There are set values in the code for the movement of wheelchair. For example the value 8 is used to move forward. Bluetooth receive this signal and send to

micro-controller to take action accordingly. A key technology which is used in the smart wheelchair system is speech recognition (voice control).

Figure 5.6: Voice Control Interface

In voice control the wheelchair is controlled through voice. When a person speaks the predefined commands like go, right, left, reverse and stop the microphone process these commands and send signal to micro-controller to perform functions accordingly. Recognition process is carried out when voice is received and recognition result is displayed on the android mobile.

5.4 Results

The proper assembling of all the components used gave us hardware of the smart wheelchair. the designed system is multi mode having controlling features of app control, voice control and joystick control. The hardware circuitry for live streaming, obstacle detection and patient health care system is also designed. The designed wheelchair system is capable of tracing its location through the use of GPS module. The developed wheelchair runs perfectly for voice command and app commands. Successfully done the hardware and software implementation.

The designed program is uploaded on the micro-controller and the designed wheelchair is tested using app, voice, gesture and joystick. The hardware runs perfectly for live streaming, location tracing and patient health care system. The designed system worked properly according to the commands given through mobile app, gesture control commands by tilting the mobile and voice control is tested using the google assistant of the android mobile. The manual control is also tested by moving the joystick in all the four directions. Qibla direction finder is also tested. In short, the designed wheelchair worked successfully for all the designed features.

6 Conclusion & Future Extensions

6.1 Conclusion

We have implemented smart wheelchair system equipped with latest technology. This type of wheelchair system can be easily implemented on large scale. The designed wheelchair contributes to the self-dependency of handicapped people. It is operating in different modes i.e. mobile control mode, joystick mode, gesture control mode and voice recognition mode. This Wheelchair is economical and affordable, that's why it is a bonus for common people. We have also add new technology in this wheelchair. The system designed is highly effective for the disabled people. This type of multi-mode wheelchair can made the person independent offering different modes of operation to the user. The running cost of this designed system is also lower making it efficient. It does not require any external help and is simple to operate. It is built to help the disabled become independent and is used for creating a connection between communication and hardware requiring less effort for controlling the wheelchair through specific mode, offering live streaming and location trace feature. An obstacle detection system is also designed in the wheelchair system which works if an emergency condition occurs. The designed wheelchair system is also equipped with patient health care system. This type of the wheelchair system will pay more attention to the health safety of the disabled people. Qibla

direction finder is also available in the smart wheelchair. The production of the designed wheelchair system will be beneficial for the hospitals to improve the comfort of the patient.

6.2 Future Extensions

Development possible for future improvements are mentioned below:

6.2.1 Alternate Power Source

DC batteries can be replaced by solar panels. Using the roof made up of solar panel can also provide protection from sun and rain.

6.2.2 Artificial Intelligence and Image Processing

Artificial intelligence (AI) technology is a system that takes information from its environment and takes intelligent decisions accordingly. Use of image processing can be beneficial in the speed controlling of the designed system on rough roads.

6.2.3 Blood Pressure Monitoring

In future advance health care options like blood pressure monitoring can also be provided in the smart wheelchair.

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Appendices

A1 Appendix - 1

A1.1 Pseudo code of the project

```
#include <Motor Shield Library>
#include <Ultrasonic sensor Library>
#include <Motor Pins>

#define Left-Motor
#define Left-Motor-RPWM
#define Left-Motor-REN
#define Left-Motor-RIS
#define Left-Motor-LPWM
#define Left-Motor-LEN
#define Left-Motor-LIS

#define Right-Motor
#define Right-Motor-RPWM
#define Right-Motor-REN
#define Right-Motor-RIS
#define Right-Motor-LPWM
#define Right-Motor-LEN
#define Right-Motor-LIS

#define Motor-Rotation
#define Motor-Debug
```

Left-Motor (RPWM, REN, RIS, LPWM, LEN, LIS, Rotation, Debug)
Right-Motor (RPWM, REN, RIS, LPWM, LEN, LIS, Rotation, Debug)

#define Mode-selector

Store values from mode selector in integer

#define Bluetooth-Value

Store values from Bluetooth in integer

#define Speed-Controller

Store values from speed controller in integer

#define Joystick-pins

Store values from joystick in integer

#define Gesture-pins

Store values from gesture sensor in integer

#define Ultrasonic sensor-pins

#define Higher-pin

#define Lower-pin

#define Maximum-distance

Sensor (Higher-pin, Lower-pin, Maximum-distance)

Store distance values in integer

Store duration values in integer

Store iteration values in integer

Setup function ()

{

Set value of serial communication

Set pins of mode selector as input

Set pins of speed controller as input

Set pins of joystick as input

Set pins of ultrasonic sensor as input and output

Set motor pins

Activate motor pins

Main function ()

```
{
    Read values from mode selector
    Read values from speed controller
    Read values from Joystick
    Read values from Distance Sensor

    if (mode selector value is for manual mode)
    {
        Call Manual mode function
    }
    Else if (mode selector value is for Remote mode)
    {
        Call Remote control (Mobile control) function
    }
}
```

A1.2 Controlling Functions

```
Manual Mode function ()
{
    If (values for forward function)
    {
        Call forward function
    }
    Else If (values for left function)
    {
        Call left function
    }
    Else If (values for right function)
    {
        Call right function
    }
    Else If (values for stop function)
    {
        Call stop function
    }
}
```

```
Remote Function ()
{
    If (values for forward function)
    {
        Call forward function
    }
    Else If (values for left function)
    {
        Call left function
    }
    Else If (values for right function)
    {
        Call right function
    }
    Else If (values for stop function)
    {
        Call stop function
    }
}
```

A1.3 Sub-controlling Functions

```
Forward ()
{
    Right_motor (Value from speed controller, Rotation)
    Left_motor (Value from speed controller, Rotation)
}
Left ()
{
    Right_motor (Value from speed controller, Rotation)
    Left_motor (Value from speed controller, Rotation)
}
Right ()
{
    Right_motor (Value from speed controller, Rotation)
    Left_motor (Value from speed controller, Rotation)
}
Stop ()
```

```
{
    Right_motor ()
    Left_motor ()
}
```

A1.4 Patient Care System Qibla Direction

```
#include <Library of Magnetometer>
#include <wired communication library>
#include <LCD library>
#include <Keypad Library>

#define keypad-rows
#define keypad-column
Make matrix of rows and column
Store matrix in character

#define function of keypad
#define keypad-rows pins
#define keypad-column pins

Keypad function (keypad-rows, keypad-column, matrix of rows and column)

#define HRM sensor
#define HRM-Alpha value in double
#define HRM-period value in integer
#define HRM-refresh in double

#define Qibla function
Qibla function (values)

#define LCD-pins
#define rs
#define en
#define d4
#define d5
#define d6
```

```
#define d7

LCD function (rs, en, d4, d5, d6, d7)

#define Qibla-LED

Setup Function ()
{
Set value of serial communication
Set LCD character Dimensions
Set LCD clear command
Set Wired communication
Set HRM pins as input
Set Qibla-LED pins as Output
Initialize Magnetometer for Qibla Direction
}
Main Function ()
{
    Read Values from Keypad

    If (Keypad value is for)
    {
        Set LCD Cursor
        Print (Basic need of the patient)
    }
    Else if (Keypad value for HRM Sensor)
    {
        Call HRM Sensor Function
    }
    Else
    {
        Clear LCD
    }
}
HRM Function

HRM function ()
{
```

```
        Read Values from HRM Sensor
        Calculations
        Means of all values
        Print (HRM Value)
    }

Qibla Direction

Main Function ()
{
    Set x, y, z values
    Store x, y, z values in integer
    Set Addresses for x, y, z
    Read addressor
    Convert values from addressors into 360 degrees
    Set value for Qibla
    If (value is for Qibla)
    {
        Turn ON Qibla-LED
    }
    Else
    {
        Turn OFF Qibla-LED
    }
}
```

A1.5 Location Tracing

```
#include <Software Library>
#include <GPS Library>

#define GPS-pins
#define Software Serial communication
#define GPS functions
Store GPS dump values in function
Store Footprint values in function

Setup Function ()
{
```

```
Set Serial Communication values
Set GPS Serial communication values
Print GPS Name
Print GPS Size Number
Print new line
}
Main Function ()
{
Read data from GPS
Calculations
Set Altitude
Set Longitude
Read Mean values
Map mean values
Calculations
Read Altitude values
Take means of Altitude values
Read Longitude Values
Take Means of Longitude values
Print Altitude
Print Longitude
Print New Line
}
```

A1.6 Live Streaming

```
#include 'camera module'
#include <camera module library>
#include <wifi library>
#include 'soc functions'
#include 'soc controlling function'
#include 'camera pins'
#define Camera AI
Set Wifi name
Set wifi password

Camera AI Server Function
```

```
#include 'esp server'
#include 'esp timer'
#include 'esp camera'
#include 'image converter'
#include 'camera index'

#define camera en-roller time
#define Face ID saver
#define Face-color- colors
#define camera index matrix []

Setup Function ()
{
  Set serial communication values
  Set Serial debug output
  Set serial print
  Configure camera function
  Configure channel
  Configure Timer
  Configure GPIOs
  Configure Clock
  Configure synchronization
  If (found)
  {
    Configure frame size
    Configure image quality
  }
  Else
  {
    False
  }
  Wifi functions start
  If (connected)
  {
    Print wifi connected
    call web server function ()
  }
  Else
```

```
{  
Print wifi not connected  
}  
}  
Main function ()  
{  
Delay of 10 seconds  
}
```

A2 Appendix - 2

A2.1 Schematics of the developer board

USB to Serial Converter

Power Configuration

LEDs

RESET

Figure A2.1: Schematics of Developer Board

AtMega2560

Figure A2.2: Schematics of Developer Board

Figure A2.3: Schematics of Developer Board